

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

Horizon 2020 Research Infrastructures GA n° 101004730

DELIVERABLE REPORT

Potential AM applications in accelerators

DELIVERABLE: D10.1

Document identifier:	IFAST-D10.1
Due date of deliverable:	End of Month 30 (Oct 2023)
Report release date:	25/10/2023
Work package:	WP10: Advanced Accelerator Technologies
Lead beneficiary:	PoliMi
Document status:	Final

ABSTRACT

This report deals with the output of a survey on the application of Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies in the field of particle accelerators. The current applications, further needs and perspective developments foreseen for the accelerator community are discussed.

The document consists of a first part where a literature survey of existing applications of AM to accelerators has been made. An analysis of the needs for the accelerator community is then presented, followed by a discussion about the opportunities offered by AM for accelerators in particle physics and for technology transfer to accelerators for other industrial fields.

Finally, the design activities, manufacturing and testing of a proof-of-concept RFQ sector built by AM are described. The dissemination of this output to the widest possible audience is considered as an important strategy to raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101004730. IFAST began in May 2021 and will run for 4 years.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Partner	Date
Authored by	M. Vedani ¹ , T. Romano ^{1,2} , G. Pikurs, ² A. Ratkus ² , T. Torims ² , N. Delerue ³ , F. Brukner ⁴ , E. Lopez ⁴ , S. Gruber ⁴ , M. Pozzi ⁵ , M. Foppa Pedretti ⁵ , M. Thielmann ⁶ , P. Wagenblast ⁶	¹ PoliMi ² RTU ³ CNRS ⁴ Fraunhofer IWS ⁵ Roesler ⁶ TRUMPF	04/10/2023
Reviewed by	M. Vretenar [on behalf of Steering Committee]	CERN	25/10/2023
Approved by	Steering Committee		25/10/2023

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1 INTRODUCTION.....5

2 SURVEY OF EXISTING AM APPLICATIONS.....6

2.1 THE EVOLVING SCENARIO OF AM 6

2.2 LITERATURE SURVEY..... 8

2.3 REVIEW OF AM APPLICATIONS IN ACCELERATORS 15

3 ANALYSIS OF NEEDS FOR THE ACCELERATOR COMMUNITY23

3.1 QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT USE OF AM IN ACCELERATOR COMPONENTS 23

3.2 ACTIONS TO RAISE CONFIDENCE IN AM 24

4 POTENTIAL AM APPLICATIONS IN ACCELERATORS25

4.1 OPPORTUNITIES FOR ACCELERATORS IN PARTICLE PHYSICS AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER TO OTHER INDUSTRIAL FIELDS 25

4.2 DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF A RFQ FOR ACCELERATORS..... 26

4.2.1 *1/4 RFQ prototype* 27

4.2.2 *Full-size RFQ module*..... 29

4.2.3 *Performance evaluation for usage in accelerators* 30

5 PERSPECTIVE DEVELOPMENTS33

6 CONCLUSION34

7 REFERENCES.....35

ANNEX: GLOSSARY39

Executive summary

The report presents a summary of the activities carried out and of the output achieved within task 10.2 about the survey on additive manufacturing (AM) applications in accelerators. The main needs for the accelerator community and perspective developments aimed at increasing confidence and awareness about opportunities and limitations offered by the AM technology are discussed.

In particular, chapter two of the deliverable contains a short historical description of the evolution of AM machines and market since their birth, dating back to the mid-1980s. A list of the known scientific documents available in the open literature about application of AM to accelerators is then provided. Finally, a detailed survey of AM applications in the accelerator field follows, in an attempt to describe potential opportunities and highlight the challenges still to be faced.

Chapter three is aimed at analysing further needs that would speed up the uptake of AM in the community. The output of a survey carried out within the frame of a joint activity between task 10.2 and 10.3 of the I.FAST project are briefly recalled. It is concluded that the particle-accelerator community apparently feels the lack of knowledge about specific topics which represent the next challenges to be faced in a near future. These include: materials, with their strict requirements on purity, lack of defects and well known properties; size, geometrical accuracy and surface roughness of the printed parts; additional peculiar part properties such as vacuum tightness, outgassing rate, electrical conductivity, high-voltage holding.

Chapter four summarizes the opportunities of AM for accelerators in particle physics and the expected technology transfer to other industrial fields of societal importance. A further section describes the outputs of activities, currently in progress, to stimulate the interest and raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community. Specifically, the research team has been engaged in the design, manufacturing, and characterisation of a radio-frequency quadrupole proof of concepts manufactured as copper single parts by an innovative Laser-powder bed fusion AM technology based on a green laser source. Promising results have been collected and directions for future development have been identified.

Finally, perspective developments are discussed, highlighting the expected innovations which will become available in the near future on the market, with the hope of stimulating a shift of AM components for accelerators from the prototyping to the production stage.

1 Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is a recent and fast-evolving technology which is promptly becoming an integral part of the advanced technological portfolio available for the most demanding industrial applications. Within the accelerator community, AM is apparently progressing at a slow pace, owing to traditionalism, lack of knowledge, and skepticism about the compliance with the stringent accelerator requirements.

The present document summarizes the output of activities carried out within task 10.2 (Additive Manufacturing – Survey of applications and potential developments) of the I.FAST project. The main objectives of the task consist in identifying the needs for future and faster development, identifying technology barriers and challenges, and defining the future strategic directions to foster the impact of AM on accelerator applications.

2 Survey of existing AM applications

2.1 THE EVOLVING SCENARIO OF AM

The roots of AM date back to the mid-1980s when a method for the fast production (originally called rapid prototyping) of full-size prototypes to test functionalities and shapes of components was patented by Charles Hull (figure 1). Few years later the first AM technology based on polymer Stereolithography (SLA) was granted the first patent and commercialized. By SLA, UV light-sensitive liquid polymers could solidify under the action of a laser, producing 3D models faster and with fairly good accuracy.

In 1992, Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) was introduced, which allowed the selective melting, layer by layer, of powdered polymers to form a solid object. Within few years the same concept was extended to metal powders for the production of metal prototypes featuring not only functional properties, but also the structural strength required for the real use of the printed objects.

Figure 1: The timeline of discovery and development of Additive Manufacturing [1].

As a matter of fact, the very first metal AM system was launched in 1994 by EOS using the term Direct Metal Laser Sintering (DMLS) since the metal parts were produced using two-component metal powders through a sintering process activated by the laser source (a low-melting matrix such as copper or bronze melted around the steel solid particles). In the late 90s and early 2000 high-energy laser sources were adopted to fully melt a large variety of metals and alloys, leading to the wide diffusion of the Laser-Beam Powder Bed Fusion technology (PBF-LB). Additionally, the electron beam technology was also exploited (PBF-EB) and marketed in 2002 by the Swedish company ARCAM.

For sake of completeness, parallel to the PBF technologies driven by high-energy sources, Binder Jetting (BJ) processes have also been developed since 1999. BJ makes use of a binder selectively

spread over a powder bed to produce a green solid object which is then subjected to a sintering post process to achieve full density and strength. Metal BJ stood in the shadow of PBF processes for decades and only recently became attractive for industrial application owing to the commitment of large companies such as HP and Desktop Metal.

Finally, it is to mention that Direct Energy Deposition (DED) technologies based on the deposition of molten alloys using a laser torch installed at the edge of a robot arm were already in use since many decades for coating applications. Extending the process to the AM concept by increasing the deposition rate along the z direction became an obvious development. The first commercial dedicated AM system dates back to 1998 using a Powder-Feed Laser Energy Deposition technology.

Figure 2: Present and future trend for the global metal additive manufacturing market size (in USD billion) [2].

The short historical path here discussed eventually leads us to the last decade, where the sales of metal AM machines (especially PBF-LB) and the AM market size significantly boosted and are predicted to grow at a fast rate in the years to come, as shown in figure 2. The main drivers are the consolidated maturity of this technology and the additional freedom for the design of customized parts and unconventional shapes, otherwise impossible for traditional manufacturing processes. Today, several metal parts produced by AM are currently in service for industrial applications and an increasing number is in the phase of qualification for serial production in the strategic fields of aircraft and space, medical, energy, and ground vehicles.

2.2 LITERATURE SURVEY

A comprehensive list of the of the open literature published over the years about application of AM to accelerator components is reported in table 1. From a quantitative perspective, it is readily observed that the number of papers covering AM-related topics yearly published, progressively increased along the years. A further evidence about the increasing interest in AM by the accelerator community can be evaluated through the number of contributions dealing with AM presented in the most recent years at the IPAC conference series: 0 papers in 2019 and 2020, 3 in 2021, 3 in 2022, 12 in 2023.

Table 1: Publications available from open literature about additive manufacturing applied to accelerators (W: workshop, J: journal paper, C: conference proceedings, P. Patent, T: Thesis).

Year	Title	Authors	Source	type
2005	Low-cost fabrication approach for ARIES-CS coil structure	L. Waganer (The Boeing Company)	ARIES Meeting at UCSD, San Diego (nov 2005)	W
2006				
2007	ARIES-CS coil structure advanced fabrication approach	L.M. Waganer, K.T. Slattery, J.C. Waldrop (The Boeing Company)	Fusion Science and Technology, 54 (2007) 878-889	J
2008	An ultra-high repetition rate S-band RF gun	L. Faillace et al (Università La Sapienza/INFN-LNF)	Proceedings of FEL08, Gyeongju, Korea (2008) p.282-284	C
	A novel fabrication technique for the production of RF photoinjectors	P. Frigola et al. (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Proceedings of EPAC08, Genoa, Italy (2008) p.751-753	C
	Method and apparatus for radio frequency cavity	RadiaBeam Technologies LLC, US	Patent US2008129203A1	P
2009	Development of solid freeform fabrication for the production of RF photoinjectors	P. Frigola et al. (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Proceedings of PAC09, Vancouver, BC, Canada (2009) p. 20015-2017	C
	Development of an ultra-high repetition rate S-band RF gun for the SPARX project	L. Faillace et al (Università La Sapienza/INFN-LNF)	Proceedings of PAC09, Vancouver, BC, Canada (2009) p. 1815-1817	C
2010	Development of a CW NCRF photoinjector using solid freeform fabrication	P. Frigola et al. (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Proceedings of IPAC'10, Kyoto, Japan (2010) p. 3804-3806	C
	Experimental characterization of the RF gun prototype for the SPARX-FEL project	L. Faillace et al (Università La Sapienza/INFN-LNF)	Proceedings of IPAC'10, Kyoto, Japan (2010) p. 3688-3690	C
2011	An overview of normal conduction radio frequency projects and manufacturing	R. Agustsson et al. (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Proceedings of 2011 Particle Accelerator Conference, New York, NY, USA (2011) p. 2214-2216	C

	capabilities at RadiaBeam Technologies LLC			
2012	Design of a high-precision fast wire scanner for the SPS at CERN	R. Veness et al. (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Proceedings of IBIC2012, Tsukuba, Japan (2012) p. 259-262	C
2013				
2014	Additive Manufacturing for X-band applications	A. Grudiev (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	CLIC14 Workshop, February 2014, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland	W
	Fabricating Copper Components with Electron Beam Melting	P. Frigola et al. (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Advanced Materials and Processes, 7 (2014) 20-24	J
	EBM fabrication and characterization of high-purity niobium for superconductor applications	C.A. Terrazas et al. (The University of Texas, El Paso, Tx)	Proceedings 2014 International Solid Freeform Fabrication Symposium, (2014) p. 605-616	C
	Developing an additively manufactured X-band RF load	M. Colling, A. Grudiev (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Seminar "Additive machined waveguide development" CERN (2014) https://indico.cern.ch/event/320241/	W
	Workshop "Challenges on Additive Manufacturing for High Energy Physics"		CERN (2014) https://indico.cern.ch/event/33735/	W
2015	Development of X-band high-power RF load for CLIC applications using additive manufacturing techniques	G.L. D'Alessandro (University of Salento, Lecce, Italy)	CERN-THESIS-2015-315 30/10/2015	T
	Development of nuclear quality components using metal additive manufacturing	P. Frigola (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Advanced Methods for Manufacturing Workshop Lockheed Martin (2015)	W
	Advanced additive manufacturing methods for SRF cavities of various geometries	P. Frigola et al. (RadiaBeam Technologies LLC)	Proceedings of SRF2015, Whistler, BC, Canada (2015) p. 1181-1184	C
	Experience from the construction of a new fast wire scanner prototype for the CERN SPS and its optimization for the installation in the CERN PS booster	R. Veness et al. (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Proceedings of IBIC2015, Melbourne, Australia (2015) p. 479-482	C
	Additive manufacturing method for SRF components of various geometries	RadiaBeam Technologies LLC, US	Patent US9023765B1	P

2016	Metal Additive Manufacturing Overview of the process, mechanical properties and MME facility	R. Gerard (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Workshop LHC injector upgrade. CERN (2016) https://indico.cern.ch/event/567462/	W
	3D Printing Developments	G. Romagnoli (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Workshop LHC injector upgrade. CERN (2016) https://indico.cern.ch/event/567462/	W
	Manufacturing of the first FCC-hh beam screen prototype for ANKA	C. Garion (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	WP4 Coordination meeting, EuroCirCol project (2016) https://indico.cern.ch/event/579868/	W
2017	High-Kinetic Inductance Additive Manufactured Superconducting Microwave Cavity	E.T. Holland et al. (Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Livermore, USA)	Applied Physics Letters, 111, (2017) paper # 202602	J
	Vacuum characterisation of 3D printed metals	J. Gargiulo (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Workshop FCC Week 2017. CERN (2017) https://indico.cern.ch/event/556692/	W
	Study of the suitability of 3D printing for Ultra-High Vacuum applications	S. Jenzer (LAL, Univ. Paris-Sud, CNRS/IN2P3, Orsay, France)	Journal of Physics: Conf. Series 874 (2017) paper # 012097	J
2018	Additive manufacturing of magnetic shielding and ultra-high vacuum flange for cold atom sensors	J. Vovrosh et al. (University of Birmingham, Birmingham, UK)	Scientific Reports, 8 (2018) paper # 2023	J
	Workshop “Colloque fabrication additive appliquée à la Physique des deux infinis”		LAL Orsay (2018) https://indico.ijclab.in2p3.fr/event/4990	W
	Metal 3D additive machining for in-vacuum beam instrumentation	R. Veness et al. (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Proceedings of MEDSI2018, Paris, France (2018) p. 121-124	C
	Study of the performance of a 3D printed BPM	S. Jenzer et al. (LAL, Univ. Paris-Sud, CNRS/IN2P3, Orsay, France)	Proceedings of IPAC2018, Vancouver, BC, Canada (2018) p. 3656-3659	C
	High-power conditioning of X-band RF components	N. Catalan-Lasheras et al. (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	Proceedings of IPAC2018, Vancouver, BC, Canada (2018) p. 2545-2548	C
	Additively manufactured WR-10 copper waveguide	T. Horn et al. (North Carolina State University Raleigh, US)	Proceedings of IEEE International Vacuum Electronics Conference (2018) p. 409-410	C
2019	Influence of powder particle size distribution on the printability of pure	M. Sinico et al. (KU Leuven, Belgium / INFN Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of the 30th Annual International Solid Freeform Fabrication Symposium (2019) p.657-667	C

	copper for selective laser melting			
	3D printed copper waveguides by Selective electron-beam melting process for E-band	K. Lomakin et al. (Institute of Microwaves and Photonics, FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany)	Proceedings of the 49th European Microwave Conference (2019) p. 774-777	C
	3D printing for High vacuum applications	C. R. Wolf et al. (Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften, Coburg, Germany)	Proceedings of Cyclotrons2019, Cape Town, South Africa (2019) p. 317-320	C
	Additive manufacturing of electrical and thermal devices: challenges and opportunities	P.R. Carriere et al. (RadiBeam Technologies LLC)	North American Particle Accelerator Conference 2019, Thurs, US (2019)	C
	Characteristics and processing of hydrogen-treated copper powders for EB-PBF additive manufacturing	C. Ledford et al. (North Carolina State University, US)	Applied Sciences, 9 (2019) paper # 3993	J
	Purification of selective laser melting additive manufactured niobium for superconducting RF-applications transactions on applied superconductivity	F. Motschmann et al. (CERN, Geneva, Switzerland)	IEEE Transactions on Applied Superconductivity, 29, 5 (2019) paper #3500805	J
	Is it possible to use additive manufacturing for accelerator UHV beam pipes?	S. Jenzer et al. (LAL, Univ. Paris-Sud, CNRS/IN2P3, Orsay, France)	Proceedings of IPAC2019, Melbourne, Australia (2019) p. 2240-2243	C
	Prospects of additive manufacturing for accelerators	S. Jenzer et al. (LAL, Univ. Paris-Sud, CNRS/IN2P3, Orsay, France)	Proceedings of IPAC2019, Melbourne, Australia (2019) p. 2240-2243	C
	Tests of a 3D printed BPM with a stretched wire and with a particle beam	N. Delerue et al. (LAL, Univ. Paris-Sud, CNRS/IN2P3, Orsay, France)	Proceedings of IPAC2019, Melbourne, Australia (2019) p. 2240-2243	C
	Additive manufacturing advanced technologies for accelerator applications		ARIES WP14 Workshop https://indico.cern.ch/event/775278	W
2020	Design and test of copper printed RF cavities	C. Nantista et al. (SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory, CA, US)	Proceedings of IEEE 21st International Conference on Vacuum Electronics, Monterey, CA, USA (2020) p. 149-150	C
2021	Additively manufactured ultra-high vacuum chamber for portable quantum technologies	N. Cooper et al. (University of Nottingham, UK)	Additive Manufacturing, 40 (2021) paper #101898	J

	Characterization of cryogenic material properties of 3-D-printed superconducting niobium using a 3D lumped element microwave cavity	B.T. McAllister et al. (The University of Western Australia, Crawley, WA 6009, Australia)	IEEE Transactions on Instrumentation and Measurements, 70 (2021) paper # 6002007	J
	First proof-of-concept prototype of an additive manufactured radio frequency quadrupole	T. Torims et al. (Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia)	Instruments 5, 35 (2021)	J
	Harnessing manufacturing elements to select local process parameters for metal additive manufacturing: A case study on a superconducting solenoid coil	J. Ferchow et al. (Inspire AG, Zurich, Switzerland)	Additive Manufacturing, 46 (2021) paper # 102140	J
	Workshop “Colloque fabrication additive appliquée à la Physique des deux infinis”		LAL Orsay (2021) https://indico.ijclab.in2p3.fr/event/7055	W
	First 3D printed IH-type LINAC structure – Proof-of-concept for additive manufacturing of LINAC RF cavities	H. Haehnel, U. Ratzinger (Goethe University, Frankfurt a M, Germany)	Instruments 6, 9 (2021)	J
	X-band RF spiral load optimization for additive manufacturing mass production	H. Bursali et al. (University of Lancaster, UK)	Proceeding of IPAC2021, Campinas, SP, Brazil (2021) p. 1143-1146	C
	Outgassing of Electron Beam Printed Copper	G. Lanza et al. (SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory Menlo Park, CA, US)	Proceedings of 22nd International Vacuum Electronics Conference (2021)	C
2022	Mass optimization by additive manufacturing	A.Filenius (Cornell University, NY, US / CERN, Geneva, Switzerland),	Forum on Tracking Detector Mechanics 2022, INFN/LNF. https://indico.cern.ch/event/853861/	W
	Titanium orbital welding: 3D printed parts to bulk	C. Rossi et al. (INFN Genova, Italy)	Forum on Tracking Detector Mechanics 2022, INFN/LNF. https://indico.cern.ch/event/853861/	W
	Workshop on Additive Manufacturing applications		I.FAST first Annual Meeting, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland (2021) https://indico.cern.ch/event/1133254	W

	A 3D printed pure copper drift tube linac prototype	M. Mayerhofer et al. (Bundeswehr University Munich, Germany)	Review of Scientific Instruments, 93 (2022) paper # 023304	J
	Evaluation of geometrical precision and surface roughness quality for the additively manufactured RF quadrupole prototype	T. Torims et al. (Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia)	Proceedings of IPAC2022, Bangkok, Thailand (2022) p. 787-791	C
	Dielectric loaded waveguide experimentally optimized by dispersion measurements	M. Kellermeier et al: (Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, Germany)	Proceedings of IPAC2022, Bangkok, Thailand (2022) p. 1526-1529	C
	Corrosion of copper components in the deionized water cooling system of ALBA Synchrotron light source: current research status and challenges	M. Quispe et al. (ALBA – CELLS Synchrotron, Cerdanyola del Vallès, Spain)	Proceedings of IPAC2022, Bangkok, Thailand (2022) p. 2891-2894	C
2023	Additive manufacturing of an IH-type LINAC structure from stainless steel and pure copper	H. Hähnel et al. (Goethe University, Frankfurt, Germany)	Instruments 7, 22 (2023)	J
	X-band activities at INFN-LNF	F. Cardelli et al. (INFN-LNF, Frascati, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 36-40	C
	Additive manufacturing of copper RF structures for particle accelerator applications	J. Upadhyay et al. (Los Alamos National Laboratory, Los Alamos, USA)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 47-49	C
	Development of a 704.4 MHz CH cavity using additive manufacturing	C. Zhang et al. (Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research Darmstadt, Germany)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 1726-1728	C
	Implementation of the additive manufacturing for the metal approach: the production of the accelerator grids for the DTT NBI project	A. Pepato et al. (INFN – Padua Division, Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 2201-2204	C
	Pure copper and stainless steel additive manufacturing of an IH-type LINAC structure	H. Hähnel et al. (Goethe University, Frankfurt, Germany)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4880-4883	C
	Laser powder bed fusion of pure niobium for particle accelerator applications	S. Candela et al. (INFN – Padua Division, Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4884-4887	C

Predictive capabilities in CFD simulations of additively manufactured extraction grids cooling channels for the DTT NBI system	G. Favero et al. (INFN – Padua Division, Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4888-4891	C
Additive manufacturing of 6 GHz seamless SRF copper cavities: printing, surface treatments and performance investigations	S. Candela et al. (INFN – Padua Division, Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4892-4895	C
Laser powder bed fusion of CuCrZr for nuclear fusion accelerator components	M. Bonesso et al. (INFN – Padua Division, Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4896-4898	C
Additively manufactured Ta cathode for FEBIAD type ion sources: production, geometric measurements and high temperature test	M. Ballan et al. (INFN - Laboratori Nazionali di Legnaro, Padova, Italy)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4899-4901	C
Initial high electric field vacuum arc breakdown test results for additively manufactured pure copper electrodes	A. Ratkus et al. (Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4902-4904	C
Evaluation of green laser source additive manufacturing technology for accelerator applications with ultra-high vacuum requirements	A. Ratkus et al. (Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4905-4908	C
First high-quality drift tube LINAC cavity additively manufactured from pure copper	M. Mayerhofer et al. (Universität der Bundeswehr München, Germany)	Proceedings of IPAC2023, Venice, Italy (2023) p. 4912-4915	C

2.3 REVIEW OF AM APPLICATIONS IN ACCELERATORS

A survey has been carried out to collect data about already existing accelerator components built by AM. This review will also be published in a more detailed form in [3].

To the authors' knowledge, the first application of metal AM in the accelerator sector (or nuclear physics, in broad terms) appeared in 2005, when a prototype was produced by DED for the ARIES Compact Stellarator coil structure shown in figure 3. The initial aim was to build a cost-effective shell for the magnet coil winding [3,4]. It was claimed that the final cost of the AM part was less than one-third the cost of the same structure manufactured by the conventional route.

Figure 3: ARIES-CS Stellarator coil structure without and with coils in the internal grooves [5].

Soon after the ARIES-CS Stellarator appearance, a patent was filed in the US for the manufacturing of radiofrequency cavities where “the wall of the conductive housing is made by a metal additive manufacturing technique in such a way as to produce a flow path that has a gentle trajectory without discontinuities in gradient” [6].

Frigola and co-workers, in a joint research carried out at RadiaBeam Technologies, UCLA and INFN, considered the AM technology for the design of RF photoinjectors with integrated cooling channels and improved geometry, as shown in figure 4. The output of the research was first presented at EPAC 2008 conference for a RF Gun with 100 Hz repetition rate [7] and at EPAC 2009 [8] for a 500-Hz improved version.

Figure 4: Quarter section of an RF Gun with star-shaped conformal cooling channels and snake-like channels at the coupling window shown in the inset [9].

In 2012 a new design concept for a high-precision fast wire scanner for tests in the Super Proton Synchrotron accelerator at CERN was presented. The proposal suggested the use of metal AM for the manufacturing of the beam scanning forks which support the wire, considering the requirements of lightweight and stiffness (figure 5). The technological development and qualification of the process and the manufactured prototypes were then presented in 2015 [10].

Figure 5: General view of the designed beam wire scanner (left) and details about the design of the forks (right) [11,12].

Analysing the CERN's Indico server, it appears that the first evidence of an invited lecture dedicated to AM was given by Kilburn from 3T RPD Ltd in 2012 [13]. Few ideas about potential applications in accelerators were already cited in that presentation and many other prototypes were developed in the following years at CERN, as summarized in the lecture given by Sahner of the Mechanical & Materials Engineering group [14]. The main parts manufactured by AM were titanium spacers for MQXC coils (figure 6), LHC Nb-Ti and high-field Nb₃Sn magnets, and high-temperature superconductors HTS.

In the following years, several projects based on development and manufacturing of parts by AM were activated in the European accelerator community. Among others, during the CLIC14 workshop, Grudiev presented the additively manufactured Ti6Al4V WR90 wave-guide demonstrator depicted in figure 7 [15]. It is to note that extensive testing on the printed AM samples was presented such as: DC conductivity, RF loss, leak tightness, outgassing, shape accuracy, surface roughness, mechanical strength and microstructure.

Figure 6: Additive manufactured Ti end-spacers for MQXC coils [13].

Figure 7: Additively manufactured Ti6Al4V waveguide prototype (above) and concept idea of the part (below) implementing a cooling chamber for high-power tests [15].

Further development led to the manufacturing and testing of an improved version, also shown in figure 7 featuring an extra cooling jacket, increased wall thickness, vacuum flanges, using different materials (e.g. 316L stainless steels and Ti-6Al-4V alloy) and comparing two AM processes (e.g. PBF-LB with PBF-EB) [16]. The output suggested that the electron-beam based technology was not as mature as the laser-beam technology. Moreover, issues about surface roughness and geometrical tolerances were identified as the next challenges to face for part validation [15].

In the following years the CLIC RF group at CERN published various research reports showing the results progressively achieved. An instructive survey of the developments carried out through AM for a number of RF X-band components capable to perform in high power was reported by Catalan-Lasheras and co-workers at IPAC18 conference [17]. In addition, the development of X-band spiral load was presented at IPAC2021 by Bursali [18], which eventually led to a concept for the production of RF spiral loads. A view of the spiral load is depicted in figure 8.

Figure 8: RF spiral load (cross-sectional and full model views) designed for AM production [18].

The growing interest on AM for less-conventional materials such as copper and niobium for accelerator components is confirmed by papers published already in 2014 on pure copper and on Niobium. In particular, Frigola et al. [19] produced by the PBF-EB technology copper cathodes for UCLA Pegasus 1.6 cell Photoinjector. Terrazas et al. filed a patent in US about the use of AM for SRF components of various geometries [20] and in the same year published a report on fabrication and characterization of high-purity Nb for superconductor applications claiming that AM technology was a promising alternative to conventional forming, leading to significant advantages for uniform wall thicknesses, improved structure rigidity and material purity [21].

More detailed information about the performance of a RF single cavity based on Fermilab's 3.9 GHz 3rd harmonic cavity design and incorporating stiffening 3D lattice supports (see figure 9) was reported in [22,23]. However, it is to remark that the part was still made by two parts and the process included additional steps of internal surface machining, polishing and final EB welding.

In 2014 a first event fully dedicated to AM topics was organized at CERN [24]. The AM workshop was split into two sessions about metal powders and about polymers & substrates, gathering a total of 115 attendees, with a broad range of talks covering materials, processing and applications.

Further typical applications where opportunities offered by AM can be more efficiently exploited are given by heat exchangers. In 2015, the WP3 research team of the LIEBE project considered the advantages of metal AM for the design and manufacturing of lead-bismuth/water heat exchangers, eventually proposing the prototype depicted in figure 10 [25].

Figure 9: view of the single-cell cavity produced by and produced by PBF-EB technology [22].

Figure 10: Additively manufactured lead-bismuth eutectic/water heat exchanger [25].

Over the years, the increased awareness about AM potential applications, also rose the request for more accurate characterization of material behaviour after AM processing. The testing facilities and protocols available at CERN have been documented in [26,27]. Specific studies to prove vacuum tightness of part produced by PBF-LB have been carried out by French scientists from LAL and CNRS/IN2P3. Type DN40KF tubes produced by two different manufacturers with 316L stainless steels by PBF-LB showed promising results [28]. In a following step, beam pipe monitors featuring a more complex shape (figure 11) were designed and tested to prove the effectiveness of AM processing for such parts requiring high alignment tolerances [29].

Figure 11: Additively manufactured DN40KF tubes for vacuum tests (left) [26] and BPM prototypes (right) [29].

A dedicated test for vacuum tightness and outgassing using the membranes (ISO KF or CF type) shown in figure 12 is also in use at CERN. The first review of applicability for AM materials was reported in 2016 [27]. Tests carried out on AM printed membranes made of different materials [30] showed that in general stainless steel 316L is helium leak tight with thicknesses exceeding 0,25mm, Ti and Al post-processed by hot isostatic pressing (HIP) are helium tight only above 0,5mm. However, it was observed that these limits are strongly influenced by the manufacturing process and printing parameters.

Figure 12: AM ISO-KF type vacuum test membrane 3D model, drawing and test assembly. [27].

Beam dumps represent a further application in the accelerator field where the design can benefit from opportunities offered by AM. Beam dumps are designed to stop the proton beam of a cyclotron at the end of a beamline. As such, they need to include water cooling channels to control the working

temperature. In 2018, INFN DIAM successfully developed beam dump prototypes with internal cooling channels made of pure copper, as depicted in figure 13 [31,32].

The CERN team RADIATE introduced in 2018 a new design of AD target. The new design showed several advantages over the old version, consisting in a larger core diameter, the use of a multi material configuration (Ta, Ir) and expanded graphite as matrix material. Similarly to the above beam dumps, the design included a double wall Ti-6Al-4V assembly with an internal spiral channel for pressurized compressed air cooling [12,33]. The new targets produced by PBF-LB technology at CERN's AM workshop are shown figure 14.

Figure 13: AM pure copper beam dump prototype [32].

Figure 14: Ti-6Al-4V PROTAD target housings produced by PBF-LB [12].

Finally, it is worth recalling that task 10.4 of I.FAST project also foresees the manufacturing of SRF cavities using the PBF-LB technology. These activities have been reported in deliverable D10.3 “Additive-manufactured SRF Cavities” by the lead partner DIAM (INFN Padua Division).

The main aim of the task was to evaluate AM reliability for the manufacturing of seamless 6 GHz SRF cavities. Among others, complete pure-copper cavities could be produced (see figure 15) without internal supports and with flanges at their edges to perform leak tests, cryogenic tests and for surface finishing optimization.

Figure 15: Copper (left) and Niobium (right) SRF cavities produced by L-PBF at DIAM-INFN within the activities of task 10.4 (pictures adapted from Deliverable D10.3).

Niobium samples and cavity prototypes were then developed. With the aim of improving the as built downward-facing surface quality, contour parameters and innovative contactless support structures were investigated, eventually allowing the successful printing of the pure-Niobium cavities also shown in figure 15.

3 Analysis of needs for the accelerator community

3.1 QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT USE OF AM IN ACCELERATOR COMPONENTS

Within the frame of a joint activity between task 10.2 and 10.3 of the I.FAST project, a survey has been made toward the accelerator community to evaluate the current confidence, concerns and needs for the production and repair of accelerator components. The output of this survey has already been described in Deliverable D10.2: “Survey of AM applications and strategies for repairing components by AM” submitted in April 2023. Only the most relevant issues will be recalled in this report to support further analyses.

It is worth considering that the questionnaire was circulated through the IFAST project newsletter to 290 project members from 49 participating institutions and 32 associate partners in 14 countries in March 2022. After three months, the feedback was limited to 21 responses, corresponding to a 7,2% response rate.

Data showed that the participants were mainly accelerator-hardware experts or designers and they were already aware about the opportunities offered by AM. When enquiring whether they would consider AM for the manufacturing of accelerator components, 81% replied positively while 9% suggested that AM could be an option only for the future. A long list of accelerator components which might benefit from AM was identified, which includes most of the parts already described in section 2.2, e.g.: cavities, drift tubes, complex shapes with cooling circuits and heat exchangers, supports for sensors and magnets. Considering the expected challenges, material properties, final cost, control of surface roughness and porosity were the concerns most frequently cited.

In conclusion, it was inferred that the accelerator community is being carefully considering AM (both for manufacturing and repair of components), but it is not yet fully enthusiastic about current achievements. There exists a wide list of already-identified components which would potentially benefit from the advantages offered by AM such as design freedom, manufacturing flexibility and processing ability of otherwise critical materials. However, few objective technical challenges, together with a sort of traditionalism and reluctance to change design paradigms, still represent barriers for the uptake of AM.

3.2 ACTIONS TO RAISE CONFIDENCE IN AM

From the above-described survey, it appears that the field of particle accelerator is looking at AM technologies with great attention, but the number of tested and validated accelerator parts produced by AM is still limited and it is growing at slower rate than for the other similar sectors already cited. There exists a fair awareness that AM is not a “magic tool” for any technical concern since it can offer advantages but also challenges. The AM technology is continuously improving, making available advanced machines with larger build volumes and almost fully automated processes, new software tools for the so-called “design for additive manufacturing” and for accurate process simulation.

However, the particle-accelerator community apparently feels the lack of knowledge about specific topics which represent the next challenges to be faced in a near future to raise confidence and reduce skepticism in AM. They can be grouped into the following three key points.

- Materials for most accelerator components have strict chemical-purity requirements, they must show uniform microstructure, lack of manufacturing defects, residual stresses and well-known properties.
- The size of components may exceed the printing volume of many AM commercial systems while the requirements for geometrical accuracy and surface roughness of accelerator parts are often very demanding for most of the available AM processes.
- Peculiar material/part properties need to be carefully characterized before applications in particle accelerators, such as vacuum tightness, outgassing rate, electrical conductivity, high-voltage holding.

The analysis of the most recent literature and of the existing research projects running in Europe and worldwide confirms that the above technical gaps are being filled by virtue of the large efforts dedicated. In line with these needs, a significant contribution is being created also by the AM-group established within the partners of I.FAST WP10.

4 Potential AM applications in accelerators

4.1 OPPORTUNITIES FOR ACCELERATORS IN PARTICLE PHYSICS AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER TO OTHER INDUSTRIAL FIELDS

AM, with its multiple processing variants, including powder bed fusion, directed energy deposition and bound metal deposition technologies, is currently attracting a large interest for industrial applications in several sectors such as aerospace, medical, power generation, which very often feature demanding technical and safety requirements.

As stated, although with a slower pace, the accelerator community is also approaching AM. Components for large infrastructures in particle physics where design and manufacturing opportunities provided by AM can be exploited at best are for instance cavities, supports for sensors and magnets, cooling systems and manifolds with complex shapes, synchrotron radiation absorbers, particles sources and targets, RF guns and quadrupoles. For all of them, the most attractive opportunities consist in the ability to design new and optimized shapes which were considered as impossible to be produced by conventional manufacturing routes, along with the possible reduction of costs and usage of precious materials, and the shorter lead times. A proof-of-concept implementing these features will be described in the next section.

In addition, AM is implicitly supporting strategies toward the development of compact, more accessible and better performing accelerators to be used commercially to improve and sustain the quality of our life. Medical equipment for cancer radiation therapies (proton- and ion-therapy) and for the production of isotopes for imaging and nuclear medicine would greatly benefit from innovations in compact accelerators. Other industrial sectors for accelerators involve the sterilization for medical disposables and for food processing, the non-destructive testing of machine components by X-rays and γ -rays, the safety inspections of containers loaded on cargos, the treatments on fumes and exhaust gases to reduce the amount of pollutants.

4.2 DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF A RFQ FOR ACCELERATORS

Modern 4-vane type RFQs are conventionally manufactured by highly-conductive oxygen-free copper by multi-axis high-precision milling of pre-fabricated large-scale forged workpieces. The full section of a RFQ generally consists of four modules (see figure 16) with complex and high-tolerance manufactured surfaces that are subsequently joined together in the final 4-vane configuration by furnace brazing. A complex procedure requiring several thermal stress-release treatments during the machining steps is required to ensure that the tight tolerances are respected even after brazing. This results in a costly, time consuming, and inefficient process.

Figure 16: The CERN's LINAC 4 RFQ module [34].

It was realized that the opportunities offered by AM would be particularly suitable to improve the manufacturing aspects of RFQs by significantly reducing manufacturing time and costs and implementing improved design criteria. Eventually, complete segments including all the four vanes of the RFQ system could be built in one piece, thereby avoiding brazing and allowing for the optimal manufacturing of complex elements such as internal cooling channels and external ports [34]. RFQ manufacturing also features several strict requirements which make the development of an AM prototype rather challenging. These are summarized in table 2.

Table 2: Main technical requirements for the RFQ prototype [34].

Requirement	Target value
Geometrical accuracy	20 μm on vane tip, 100 μm elsewhere
Surface roughness	Ra = 0,4 μm for all inner surfaces
Vacuum tightness	10^{-7} mbar
Electrical conductivity	90% IACS
Peak electric field on surface	≈ 40 MV/m

For these reasons, a RFQ prototype to be produced by AM (specifically by PBF-LB) was designed, produced and subjected to functional tests within the activities of task 10.2 of I.FAST project.

To the authors' knowledge, the output represents the very first proof-of-concept confirming that AM manufactured RFQs are feasible and achievable. Its dissemination to the widest possible audience was considered to be an important strategy to raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community.

4.2.1 ¼ RFQ prototype

A first proof-of-concept of the RFQ was intended to reproduce one quarter of a compact 750 MHz RFQ reaching the energy of 5MeV in a length of 2 meters, which was recently developed at CERN for applications in the medical and detection fields [35].

A model of the RFQ quarter with a length of 95 mm was designed based on AM manufacturing capabilities and opportunities. The RFQ shows a quadrupolar symmetry, therefore, all peculiar features can be included within a 90° sector design, as shown in figure 17. The quarter-sector prototype includes the vane tip reproducing the original design geometry, the inner surfaces, and a re-designed inner structure implementing conformal cooling channels to optimize the thermal service conditions and consisting of a honeycomb pattern which replaces the original massive sections.

Figure 17: RFQ quarter section designed for AM [34].

Full details about the design have been published in [34]. The proof-of-concept was built by project partner Fraunhofer IWS with pure copper, using a TruPrint1000 Green Edition PBF-LB system equipped with a green laser providing a wavelength of 515 nm (more suitable to maximize the laser absorption for copper) and a maximum laser power of 500 W. The 3D print job took 16 hours and 29 minutes for a total height of 98 mm, produced by 3267 print layers of thickness 30 μm each. Figure 18 depicts the as built prototype. It is to remark that the wall thickness of the honeycomb structure was set to 0,6 mm, resulting in a volume reduction of 37% with respect to the massive design.

This first prototype enabled to evaluate some preliminary aspects of concern for AM parts, such as the achievable geometrical accuracy and the surface roughness. As far as the first topic is concerned, 3D optical scan measurements carried out at Fraunhofer IWS (see figure 19) showed that the largest deviation of 0,31 mm at the vane tip was found at the bottom of the printed part, close to the support

structures, presumably due to the compliance of the supports and the shrinkage stresses generated during processing. Apart from this deviation, which will be compensated in future designs, the deviations along the vane tip decreased down to 0,02-0,04 mm.

Figure 18: As built RFQ quarter section still jointed through its supports to the build platform [34].

Figure 19: 3D optical scanning set-up for the evaluation of the geometrical accuracy of the RFQ prototype (left) and comparison of the measured point cloud with original CAD data (right) [34].

Surface roughness is a challenging requirement for high-precision accelerator components produced by AM. The mean arithmetical surface roughness (Ra) measured on the quarter RFQ prototype was about 14 μm , as opposed to the required Ra = 0,4 μm . Although further improvements could be

achieved by the optimization of the process parameters, it is reasonable to consider finishing as a mandatory post-processing operation to achieve the target roughness value.

Investigations have been carried out to establish opportunities and limitations of some reference surface finishing technologies for the reduction of the surface roughness of the quarter RFQ prototype, especially in the region of the vane tips. The main results have been published in [36]. Surface mass finishing with abrasive media, water and additives was first considered using vibrating and rotating machines made available by project partner Rösler. Chemically-assisted surface finishing was a further step adopted by Rösler, consisting in the combination of the mechanical abrasion promoted by abrasives for mass finishing and the chemical reactions induced by suitable reactants. Finally, a proprietary MMP Technology surface finishing was also investigated. A summary of the achieved roughness values is reported in table 3 [36]. The data demonstrate that the roughness target can be achieved or at least closely approached, and all the finishing processes can be good candidates for the finishing of accelerator components. It is to remark that other finishing technologies are available and will be considered in the future.

Table 3: Surface roughness of the quarter RFQ before and after surface finishing [36]. The two measurement values of the finished samples refer to the two sides of the vane tips.

Finishing method	Ra (µm)	Rz (µm)
As built	13,82	48,86
Mass finishing	0,09 / 0,07	0,83 / 0,58
Chemically-assisted finishing	0,07 / 0,12	0,67 / 0,97
MMP Technology	0,30 / 0,11	3,24 / 1,03
Target value	0,4	Not specified

4.2.2 Full-size RFQ module

Based on the investigation carried out on the first quarter RFQ proof of concept, two full-size RFQ sectors were subsequently designed, implementing a set of improved features and a size compatible with current compact linear accelerator RFQs.

Figure 20: Full-size RFQ design (left) and view of the printed part [36].

Figure 21: View of the as built second full-size RFQ (source: www.trumpf.cn/en_CN/products/machines-systems/additive-production-systems/truprint-5000-green-edition) and a detail of the printed part.

The copper RFQ demonstrators have been printed with a new model TruPrint 5000 PBF-LB system recently launched on the market by project partner TRUMPF. The system features a green laser source and a larger process chamber allowing to build volumes of 300 mm in diameter and 400 mm in height. A first full-section RFQ segment was produced with a total length of 248 mm and a cross-section diameter of 148 mm, as described in [36]. The print process took about 110 hours for a total of about 6400 layers of 40 μm thickness each. The new design takes advantage of an improved high-resolution CAD model, optimized shape of the cooling channels and of the internal lattice structure. It implements flanges for vacuum tests and orifices and for RF tests. Figure 20 depicts the design of the RFQ sector and the corresponding printed workpiece. In a further stage, a second full-size RFQ sector with slightly larger length was produced, as shown in figure 21.

The two demonstrators are currently under investigation to complete a first set of processing and performance tests. One of the samples has been subjected to surface polishing, machining of some functional surfaces (flange planes, basal planes, bores for connections) and will be tested for vacuum tightness and RF at IJCLab.

4.2.3 Performance evaluation for usage in accelerators

To increase confidence and awareness about potential opportunities provided by AM for accelerator components, additional information is required especially on performance of the printed materials. With this objective, pure-copper samples have separately been printed for microstructure characterization, high-voltage tests and He gas tightness. Preliminary results have already been published in [37,38]. In summary, high electric-field vacuum arc breakdown tests have been carried out at CERN on pure-copper electrodes printed by AM with different levels of surface finishing (from as built rough surfaces to fully finished surfaces of both electrodes). The test setup is schematically

shown in figure 22. During the testing process, a high vacuum was maintained and the electric breakdown rate was monitored to ensure not to exceed the breakdown limit of 10^{-5} breakdowns per pulse. The initial results proved the capability of AM electrodes to hold a high electric field, while having low breakdown rates. These are crucial results for further AM technology uptake for different AM pure-copper accelerator components [37].

Figure 22: Pulsed high-voltage DC test system available at CERN and details about the anode, cathode and insulating spacer [37].

Gas tightness under ultra-high vacuum (UHV) condition is of great importance for several accelerator components. Therefore, vacuum membranes of pure copper were produced by AM using a green laser source in different thicknesses and build angles. A vacuum membrane He leak tightness test was then performed using a test setup based on a high-sensitivity mass spectrometer available at CERN (see also figure 12 in section 2.2) with sample geometry depicted in figure 23 [38]. He leakage across the membranes was tested by setting vacuum at 10^{-3} mbar in the test system, spraying pure He on the upper side of the membrane and measuring the possible flow of He across it, with a detection limit of 10^{-10} mbar·l·s⁻¹.

Figure 23: Scheme of the print orientation of the membranes and vies of the printed samples [38].

As summarized in Table 4, in the helium leakage tests of the membranes, only 3 samples out of 18 did not pass the UHV leak requirement. However, those samples reached vacuum tightness levels of

$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$, $2.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $1 \cdot 10^{-6}$ mbar·l·s⁻¹, which can be classified as water-, vapour- and virus-tight respectively.

Table 4: Summary of the He tightness test results collected on AM copper membranes [38].

Sample thickness (mm)	He tightness (mbar·l·s ⁻¹)		
	Angle		
	45°	67°	90°
2,5	Passed	Passed	Passed
2	Passed	Passed	Passed
1,5	Passed	Passed	Passed
1	Passed	Passed	Passed
0,75	Passed	Passed	$1 \cdot 10^{-5}$
0,5	Passed	$2,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-2}$

5 Perspective developments

The described analyses and surveys undoubtedly show that the community of particle accelerator is paying great attention to AM technologies, with increasing knowledge about advantages to be exploited and challenges to be faced.

The activities carried out within tasks 10.2, 10.3 and 10.4 of the I.FAST project are also contributing to attract the “curiosity” of the accelerator community and are promoting synergies among all actors having interest/activities in AM for accelerators. In particular, experimental activities are running within task 10.2 on the RFQ printed by PBF-LB (described in section 4.2). Repair technologies using AM concepts are being investigated within task 10.3, and cavities are under development in task 10.4. These actions are generally aimed at improving knowledge and confidence in AM, to fight skepticism of the most traditional designers

In a broader perspective, it can be observed that the AM technology is continuously improving, making available on the market advanced machines with larger build volumes and almost fully automated processes, new software tools to support the so-called “design for additive manufacturing” and for accurate process simulation. Research is addressing the strategic topics of multi-material AM and of hybrid manufacturing (additive + subtractive within a single machine) to offer additional degree of freedom in the design of advanced components.

Such developments are expected to stimulate new designs of accelerator components and will hopefully provide new ideas for the submission of joint research projects by the scientific community, with the final goal of shifting AM from the prototyping to production and application stage.

6 Conclusion

The main conclusions about the survey on current and potential applications of Additive Manufacturing (AM) in particle accelerators can be summarized as follows.

- The literature shows that AM applications in accelerators exist since 2005 and they are significantly growing in the most recent years. They typically include: cavities, drift tubes, complex shapes with cooling circuits and heat exchangers, supports for sensors and magnets. The adoption of AM to these parts provides advantages such as: design freedom, manufacturing flexibility and processing ability of otherwise critical materials.
- A survey has been made toward the accelerator community to evaluate the current confidence, concerns and needs for the production and repair of accelerator components. Hardware experts and accelerator-designers are already aware about the opportunities offered by AM. Most of them would currently consider AM for the manufacturing of accelerator components, while a small share (9%) considers AM as an option, but only for the future.
- The particle-accelerator community apparently feels the lack of knowledge about specific topics which represent the next challenges to be faced in the near future to raise confidence and reduce scepticism in AM: (i) materials for most accelerator components have strict requirements and need accurate characterization after being processed by AM; (ii) the size of components may exceed the printing volume while the requirements for geometrical accuracy and surface roughness of accelerator parts are often very demanding for the state-of-the-art of AM commercial systems; (iii) specific material/part properties need to be carefully characterized before applications in particle accelerators, such as vacuum tightness, outgassing rate, electrical conductivity, high-voltage holding.
- These technical gaps are being progressively filled by virtue of the large research efforts dedicated. In line with these needs, a contribution is being created also by the AM-group established within the partners of I.FAST WP10. A proof-of-concept for a RFQ sector was designed, manufactured by PBF-LB and it is currently at the testing and evaluation stage. To the authors' knowledge, this output represents the very first proof-of-concept confirming that AM-manufactured RFQ is feasible and achievable. Its dissemination to the widest possible audience is considered as an important strategy to raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community.
- The adoption of AM also suggests innovative strategies toward the development of compact, more accessible, and better performing accelerators to be used commercially to improve and sustain the quality of our life. Medical equipment for cancer radiation therapies, sterilization of devices and food processing, non-destructive testing and safety inspections, treatments of fumes and exhaust gases to reduce pollutants, are only few examples of sectors which would greatly benefit from innovations in compact accelerators.

7 References

- [1] AMPOWER Report. (2019) *Metal Additive Manufacturing history* [online]. Available from: <https://additive-manufacturing-report.com/technology/metal/metal-additive-manufacturing-history/> [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [2] Precedence Research. (2023) *Metal Additive Manufacturing Market Size, Share, Report 2022-2030* [online]. Available from: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/metal-additive-manufacturing-market> [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [3] Pikurs, G. (2023) *Research on Additive Manufacturing Technology Development for Radio Frequency Quadrupole (RFQ) Fabrication and Performance Improvement*. Riga Technical University, PhD dissertation.
- [4] Waganer, L. et al. (2005) Low Cost Fabrication Approach for ARIES-CS Coil Structure. *ARIES Meeting at UCSD*, San Diego, 17-18 November 2005.
- [5] Waganer, L. et al. (2008) ARIES-CS Coil Structure Advanced Fabrication Approach. *Fusion Science and Technology*, 54, 10, 142–149.
- [6] Agustsson, R.B. et al (2006) Method and apparatus for radio frequency cavity. *Patent US20080129203A1*
- [7] Frigola, P.; Agustsson, R.; Boucher, S.; Murokh, A.; Rosenzweig, J.; Travish, G.; Faillace, L.; Cormier, D.; Mahale, T. (2008) A novel fabrication technique for the production of RF photoinjectors *In Proceedings EPAC'08*, June 2008, Genoa, Italy. p. 751–753.
- [8] Frigola, P.; Agustsson, R.; Boucher, S.; Murokh, A.; Rosenzweig, J.; Travish, G.; Faillace, L.; Cormier, D.; Mahale, T. (2009) Development of solid freeform fabrication (SFF) for the production of RF photoinjectors. *In Proceedings EPAC'09*, May 2009, Vancouver, BC, Canada. p. 2015–2017.
- [9] Faillace, L.; Palumbo, L.; Spataro, B.; Fukasawa, A.; O'Shea, BD.; Rosenzweig, JB.; Frigola, P. (2008) An Ultra-high repetition rate S-band RF Gun. *In Proceedings FEL'08*, August 2008, Gyeongju, Korea. p. 283–284.
- [10] Veness, R.; Andreazza, W.; Chritin, N.; Dehning, B.; Emery, J.; Gudkov D.; Herranz Alvarez, J.; Magagnin, P.; Piselli E.; Samuelsson, S. (2015) Experience from the construction of a new fast wire scanner prototype for the CERN-SPS and its optimisation for installation in the CERN-PS booster. *In Proceedings IBIC2015*, September 2015, Melbourne, Australia. p. 479–482.
- [11] Veness, R.; Chritin, N.; Sirvent, J.L.; Samuelsson, S.; Koujili, M.; Emery, J.; Dehning, B.; Herranz Alvarez, J. (2012) Design of a high-precision fast wire scanner for the SPS at CERN. *In Proceedings IBIC2012*, October 2012, Tsukuba, Japan. p. 259–263.
- [12] Gerard, R. Fabrication Additive au CERN. Quelques exemples d'application. IJCLab, Orsay, France, (13.Dec.2018.) Available 447 online: https://indico.ijclab.in2p3.fr/event/4990/contributions/16695/attachments/13619/16418/I3DMetal_-_AMCERN.pdf 448 (accessed on 14/04/2022)

- [13] Kilburn, P. (2012) *Overview of Additive Manufacturing and Materials* [online]. Available from: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/214588/> [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [14] Sahner, T. (2014) *Metallic Additive Manufacturing@CERN, Workshop “Challenges on Additive Manufacturing for High Energy Physics”, November 2014*, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland. Available online: https://indico.cern.ch/event/333735/contributions/779099/attachments/651316/895585/WS_AM_05_112014_V1.pdf [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [15] Grudiev, A. (2014) *Additive Manufacturing for X-band applications. CLIC14 Workshop*, February 2014, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, Available online: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/275412/contributions/1617680/> [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [16] Colling M. (2014) *Developing an additively manufactured X-band RF load* [online]. Available from: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/320241/> [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [17] Catalan-Lasheras, N.; Damerou, H.; Gerard, R.; del Pozo Romano, V.; Grudiev, A.; McMonagle, G.; Paszkiewicz, J.; Pitman, S.; Solodko, A.; Syratcev, I.; Woolley, B.; Wuensch, W.; Vnuchenko A.; Lucas T.; Wolpi M. (2018) *High Power Conditioning of X-Band RF Components. In Proceedings IPAC2018*, May 2018, Vancouver, BC, Canada. p. 2545–2548.
- [18] Bursali, H.; Catalan-Lasheras, N.; Gerard, R.L.; Grudiev, A.; O. Gumenyuk, O.; Morales Sanchez, P.; Riffaud B.; Sauza-Bedolla, J. (2021) *High Power Conditioning of X-Band RF Components. Proceedings IPAC2021*, May 2021. Campinas, SP, Brazil. p. 1143–1146.
- [19] Frigola, P.; Harrysson, O.A.; Horn, T.J.; West, H.A.; Aman, R.L.; Rigsbee, J.M.; Ramirez, D.A.; Murr, L.E.; Medina, F.; Wicker, R.B.; Rodriguez, E. (2014) *Fabricating Copper Components with Electron Beam Melting. Journal of Advanced Materials & Processes*, 385, 20–24.
- [20] Rimmer, R.; Frigola, P.; Murock, A.Y. (2014) *Additive manufacturing method for SRF components of various geometries. Patent US9023765B1*
- [21] Terrazas, C.A.; Gaytan, S.M.; Mireles, J.; Frigola, P.; Espalin, D.; Wicker, R.B. (2014) *EBM Fabrication and Characterization of High Purity Niobium for Superconductor Applications. In Proceedings 2014 International Solid Freeform Fabrication Symposium*, August 2014, Austin, USA. p. 605–616.
- [22] Frigola, P.; Agustsson, R. B.; Faillace, L.; Murokh, A. Y.; Ciovati, G.; Clemens, W. A.; Dhakal, P.; Marhauser, F.; Rimmer, R. A.; Spradlin, J. K.; Williams, R. S.; Mireles, J.; Morton, P. A.; Wicker, R. B. (2015) *Advance Additive Manufacturing Method for SRF Cavities of Various Geometries. In Proceedings SRF2015*, September 2015, Whistler, BC, Canada. p. 1181–1184.
- [23] Frigola P. *Development of Nuclear Quality Components using Metal Additive Manufacturing. Advanced Methods for Manufacturing. (2015) Workshop Lockheed Martin*, September 2015 [online]. Available from: https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/2016/10/f34/14%20-%20Development%20of%20Nuclear%20Quality%20Components%20Using%20Metal%20Additive%20Manufacturing_5.pdf [Accessed 04 September 2023].

- [24] Workshop (2014) *Challenges on Additive Manufacturing for High Energy Physics*. November 2014, Geneva, Switzerland [online]. Available from: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/333735/> [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [25] Delonca M. (2015) *LIEBE project: WP3 – Construction and tests Project coordination meeting*. January 2015, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland [online]. Available from: https://indico.cern.ch/event/367917/contributions/1786366/attachments/731476/1003620/Melanie_LIEBE-420_WP3-coordinationmeeting-30012015.pdf [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [26] Gerard, R. (2015) *Metal Additive Manufacturing Overview of the process, mechanical properties and MME facility*. January 2015, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland [online], Available from: https://indico.cern.ch/event/567462/contributions/2293345/attachments/1353055_423/2044352/PS_DUMPREVIEW_Metal_Additive_Manufacturing_RG.pdf [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [27] Nuiry, F.X.; Romagnoli, G.; Polzin, T.; Boley, E.G.; Gerard, R. (2016) *3D Printing Developments*, October 2016. CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, [online] Available from: https://indico.cern.ch/event/567462/contributions/2293345/attachments/1353055/2044370/3D_printing_developments.pdf 435 [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [28] Jenzer, S.; Alves, M.; Delerue, N.; Gonnin, A.; Grasset, D.; Letellier-Cohen, F.; Mercier, B.; Mistretta, E.; Prevost, C.; Vion, A.; Wilmes, J.P. (2017) Study of the suitability of 3D printing for Ultra-High Vacuum applications. *Proceedings IPAC2017*. May 2017. Copenhagen, Denmark. p. 3356–3358.
- [29] Jenzer, S.; Auguste, D.; Bonis, J.; Delerue, N.; Gonnin, A.; Trofimiuk, O.; Vion, A. (2018) Study of the performances of 3D printed BPM. *Proceedings IPAC2018*, May 2018, Vancouver, BC, Canada. p. 3656–3359.
- [30] Gargiulo, J. (2017) Vacuum characterisation of 3D printed metals. *FCC Week 2017*, May 2017. Berlin, Germany [online]. Available from: https://edms.cern.ch/ui/file/1905096/1/FCCW_GARGIULO_VC_3DPM_pptx_cpdx.pdf [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [31] Sinico, M.; Cogo, G.; Benettoni, M.; Calliari, I.; Pepato, A. (2019) Influence of powder particle size distribution on the printability of pure copper selective laser melting. *Proceedings SSFS2019*, June 2019, Texas, USA. p. 657–667.
- [32] Bonesso, M. (2019) SLM Development on Copper and Copper Alloy for Nuclear Fusion Physics. *Additive Manufacturing Workshop 2019*. September 2019. INFN, Padova, Italy, [online]. Available from: https://agenda.infn.it/event/19247/contributions/100154/attachments/66906/82004/BONESSO_-452_wokshop_20_settembre_2019_-_Massimiliano_Bonesso.pdf [Accessed 04 September 2023].
- [33] Torregrosa, C.; Calviani, M.; Perillo-Marccone, A.; Solieri, N.; Canhoto, J.; Ferriere, R.; Coiffet, T.; Timmins, M.; Fornasiere, E.; Grenier-Boley, E.; Seidenbinder, R.; Grenier, D.; Busom, J.; Sorlut, S.; Butcher, M.; Grec, L.; Sola, J.; Guinchard, M.; Bianchi, L.; Gerard, R.; Redondas, M.; Bergeret, M.; Porret, A.; Dickinson B. (2018) PROTAD Target and HRMT-48 Experiment,

Relevance for BIDs. CERN, Geneva, Switzerland, (20.Dec.2018.) Available online: <https://indico.cern.ch/event/718767/contributions/3232507/> (accessed on 14/04/2022)

- [34] Torims, T.; Pikurs, G.; Gruber, S.; Vretenar, M.; Ratkus, A.; Vedani, M.; López, E.; Brückner, F. (2021) First Proof-of-Concept Prototype of an Additive Manufactured Radio Frequency Quadrupole. *Instruments*, 5, 35, paper 5040035.
- [35] Vretenar, M.; Dimov, V. A.; Garlasché, M.; Grudiev, A.; Koubek, B.; Lombardi, A. M.; Mathot, S.; Mazur, D.; Montesinos, E.; Timmins, M. (2016) High-frequency compact RFQs for medical and industrial applications. *Proceedings IPAC2016*, May 2016, East Lansing, MI, USA. p. 704-709.
- [36] Ratkus, A.; Torims, T.; Pikurs, Krogere, D.; Vretenar, M.; Cherif, A.; Gruber, S.; Lopez, E.; Pozzi, M.; Foppa Pedretti, M.; Wagenblast, P.; Thielmann, M.; Vedani, M.; Delerue, N.; Otto, T. (2022) Evaluation of geometrical precision and surface roughness quality for the additively manufactured radio frequency quadrupole prototype. *Proceedings IPAC2022*, June 2022, Bangkok, Thailand. p. 787-791
- [37] Ratkus, A.; Torims, T.; Pikurs, G.; Bjelland, V.; Calatroni, S.; Peacock, R.; Serafim, C.; Vretenar, M.; Wuensch, W.; Vedani, M.; Romano, T.; Pozzi, M.; Foppa Pedretti (2023) Initial high electric field vacuum arc breakdown test results for additively manufactured pure copper electrodes. *Proceedings IPAC2023*, May 2023, Venice, Italy. p. 4902–4904.
- [38] Ratkus, A.; Torims, T.; Pikurs, G.; Laciš, V.; Garion, C.; Kos, H.; Rorison, S.; Gruber, S.; López, E.; Stepien, L.; Patil, A.; Vedani, M. (2023) Evaluation of green laser source additive manufacturing technology for accelerator applications with ultra-high vacuum requirements. *Proceedings IPAC2023*, May 2023, Venice, Italy. p. 4905-4908.

Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AM	Additive Manufacturing
BJ	Binder Jetting
CLIC	Compact Linear Collider
DED	Directed Energy Deposition
DMLS	Direct Metal Laser Sintering
HIP	Hot Isostatic Pressing
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
PBF-LB	Powder Bed Fusion by Laser Beam
PBF-EB	Powder Bed Fusion by Electron Beam
RF	Radio Frequency
RFQ	Radio-Frequency Quadrupole
SLA	StereoLitography (Apparatus)
SLS	Selective Laser Sintering
SRF	Superconducting Radio Frequency
UHV	Ultra-High Vacuum